

Impact of Nozzle Guide Vanes on the Pressure Field Inside a Rotating Detonation Combustor

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In order to better understand the circumferential structure of the pressure field inside an RDC and the influence of discrete outlet boundary conditions on the pressure field, experiments were conducted with dynamic and static pressure measurements based on five pairs of PCBs and CTAPs mounted along the axial direction of the RDC and a set of nozzle guide vanes (NGVs) installed behind the combustor exit. The mass flow rate and outlet restrictions are varied to investigate their effects on wave propagation and pressure rise in the RDC. Additionally, a simulated pressure map from a fast reactive Euler solver is compared with experimental results in this study. It was found that under a single wave (SW) operating mode condition, there are four components in one detonation lap that can be observed based on the phase-averaged pressure at four axial locations along the combustion chamber. The detonation/oblique shock wave and the inlet reflection generated by the collision of the detonation front and the inlet boundary propagate downstream, while the two outlet reflections propagate upstream when the oblique shock and the inlet reflection meet the outlet boundary. The mass flow rate variation resulted in a slight increase in the oblique shock angle from 50.0° to 51.4° . The outlet restriction made a significant contribution to the pressure profile at the combustor exit, compressing the oblique shock angle from 65.4° to 50.0° . NGVs allow the flow to pass through the combustor exit and meanwhile reflections between NGVs can also be reflected back, thereby significantly reducing the outlet reflections compared with uniform outlets. The results from reactive Euler simulations are in good agreement with the experimental map established in this study, showing that the oblique shock angle deviation between two maps is less than 3° , and the principal components determined based on the experiments can be observed in the simulated pressure map. This work helps to understand the dynamics of the pressure field in the combustor and explore the possibilities of RDCs in gas turbine applications.

Symbols

A = area
 \dot{m} = mass flow rate
 α = oblique shock angle
 p = pressure
 θ = azimuthal position

Abbreviations

UR = uniform outlet restriction
NGVR = nozzle guide vanes outlet restriction

Station Numbers

3.2 = combustion annulus
8 = outlet throat

I. Introduction

Increasing the turbine inlet temperature is an effective method to improve gas turbine thermal efficiency, but there are hardware limitations due to the need for advanced high-temperature resistant materials and additional cooling systems [1]. Pressure gain combustion (PGC) is a promising technology to overcome turbine inlet temperature challenges and achieve higher efficiencies by replacing traditional thermodynamic cycles with detonation-based cycles, which generate less entropy, but an increase in stagnation pressure throughout the combustor [2, 3]. Rotating detonation combustion (RDC) is one of the most popular PGC implementations in recent years due to its compact size and the absence of

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periodic ignition [4, 5]. Kayser et al. [6] implemented three techniques, including the Kiel probe method [7], the equivalent available pressure method (EAP), and the Mach-corrected CTAP method, to measure the total pressure at the combustor exit and the pressure gain throughout the combustion chamber. In their experiment they found a maximum stagnation pressure gain of -0.07, indicating that RDC is expected to achieve positive pressure gain.

Conventional combustor diagnostic techniques are often applied to RDC performance evaluation, such as measurements of pressure, luminosity, heat flux, operating mode, etc. [8, 9]. Pressure measurement is a commonly used technology in RDC development due to its cost and ease of implementation. PCB and Kulite are two representatives, used to measure dynamic pressure and static pressure in RDC respectively. RDC has unstable combustion, supersonic propagation, and high-enthalpy products [10], so to extend the survival time of sensors in the harsh environment of an RDC, they are often installed in recessed, capillary tube averaged pressure (CTAP) and infinite tube pressure (ITP) configurations, although the pressure will be attenuated to varying degrees as a cost.

Phase-averaging is a common processing method to obtain the circumferential structure of the pressure signals in the RDC. Bohon et al. [11] investigated the phase-averaged dynamic pressure of PCB sensors using the arithmetic mean method, and compared the pressure profile and peak height with varying equivalence ratios and mass flow rates. The results show that as the mass flow rate increases, the peak pressure increases continuously. Some follow-up studies by Tagliaferri et al. [12] described a new technique based on dynamic time warping (DTW), which shows that the soft DTW averaging method has better performance in capturing key features of pressure traces in RDCs, resulting in a more representative average pressure. However, this technique is still under development and the impact of the smoothing parameter γ in the soft DTW package on the phase averaging results requires further study. Therefore, the present study will use the conventional arithmetic mean method to obtain the phase average pressure.

Different operating modes were observed in the RDC, including two counter-rotating waves[13], a clear single wave and its counter-rotating components [14], multiple waves[15] and longitudinal wave [16]. These operating modes are associated with distinct flow fields and pressure distributions inside combustion chamber. The focus of this study is therefore to build a pressure field map that presents the circumferential structure inside the RDC, so the rotation mode can be studied. As a first step and in order to minimize the difficulties in phase averaging and pressure feature identification, here only clear single wave modes (SW) with a dominant frequency around 6 kHz will be focused on.

One possible application of the RDC is to extract work through a turbine, but the unsteady nature and harsh environment of the RDC make turbine integration challenging. Bach et al. [17] designed a discrete outlet boundary at the RDC exit by integrating a set of nozzle guide vanes (NGVs), and showed that the NGVs do not significantly affect the operating mode, but can affect the direction of the detonation wave and reduce pressure fluctuations. Ding et al. [18] investigated two NGV configurations, normal and inverse installation, on the RDC performance. They found out NGVs can improve the stability of the detonation and decrease the pressure oscillation.

Numerical simulations can eliminate the risk of sensor damage and provide predictions for the wave propagation inside the RDC. Yao et al. simulated the 3D RDC and investigated the stability of rotating detonation waves inside the combustor [19, 20]. The results show that the collision of counter rotating waves is likely to generate a new detonation front in the combustor, which causes the initiation-quenching-reinitiation of the system, and the increase in the number of detonation waves shows a negative effect on the propagation velocities. Klopsch et al.[21] developed a fast reactive Euler solver based on TU Berlin's RDC. It provides the capability for investigating the influence of the combustor geometries, mass flux and equivalence ratio on the RDC performance. The simulated pressure field map and oblique shock angle will be compared with the experimental results in this study.

There are few studies on the quantification of the pressure field inside the RDC as well as the influence caused by NGVs on the pressure field based on actual experimental data. Therefore, in this study, a pressure field map based on phase-averaged pressure will be established, and a set of nozzle guide vanes will be installed downstream of the RDC to study the influence of discrete boundaries on the pressure field. This will help the community to better understand the mechanisms of pressure variations in the combustor and the possibilities for turbine integration.

II. Experimental setup

Figure 1 shows a cross-section of TU Berlin's RDC. Hydrogen is injected axially into the combustor through 100 holes with a diameter of 0.5 mm, while air is injected radially inward through a 1 mm slot into the combustor, which generates 282.7 mm² injector area, and mixes with the fuel in the jet in a cross-flow configuration. For all tests in this study, the equivalence ratio was fixed at 1. The outer annulus diameter is 90 mm and the annular width between the inner wall and the outer wall is 7.6 mm. In order to install nozzle guide vanes behind the combustor exit, a 190 mm length outer body that extends the 110 mm combustion chamber section is used, allowing the installation of up to 18

Fig. 1 TU Berlin’s RDC with five PCBs and five CTAPs installed along the combustor axial direction, and NGVs installed downstream of the detonation region.

nozzle guide vanes.

Pressure was measured by five PCB sensors in recessed cavity and five Kulite sensors in CTAP configuration, mounted in parallel along the the combustor axial direction to study the full picture of the pressure field in the combustion chamber. The fuel plate determines the zero line for the axial dimensions, and the first pair of sensors is located at 25.6 mm downstream. Each following pair of sensors is installed in 23 mm increments. The front ends of the NGVs are located between the fourth and the fifth pairs of sensors. Both dynamic and static pressure data were sampled by the DAQ system at 500 kHz.

Three mass flow rates of 400 g/s, 450 g/s, and 500 g/s are tested in this study to ensure that only single wave modes (SW) can be produced, thereby reducing the complexity of the phase averaging. Two sets of outlet restrictions were used, including a set of the uniform outlet plates providing 0%, 16%, 25% and 33% blockage, and nozzle guide vanes providing 17% and 33% blockage with 9 and 18 NGVs installed respectively.

III. Results and Discussion

This study attempts to identify the oblique shock wave and the propagation of reflections inside the RDC based on the corresponding pressure features at each axial location along the combustor, and further build a pressure map showing the circumferential structure of the pressure field in the RDC. The phased-averaged pressure is measured by a combination of five PCB sensors and CTAPs along the RDC axial direction. The effects of the mass flow rate and outlet restriction on RDC operation is investigated. In particular, a set of nozzle guide vane proxies are compared with uniform outlet restrictions to further explore the application possibilities of the RDC with turbomachinery. Lastly, the experimentally measured pressure field map is compared to simulation results from a fast reactive Euler solver.

A. Phase-averaged pressure extraction

Accurate pressure measurement and phase average pressure extraction are the prerequisites for building a pressure field map. In order to obtain a complete static pressure profile while protecting the sensors from the harsh environment inside the RDC, the pressure in this study was measured through five pairs of PCBs and CTAPs installed at different axial locations of the combustor. Figure 2(a) shows, at 25.6 mm of the combustor axial direction, the dynamic pressure measured by a PCB and the static pressure measured by a CTAP, respectively with the 33% outlet restriction and 500 g/s mass flow rate. It can be seen that ignition starts at 0.05 s, followed by the pressure increasing after ignition, and settling gradually to a steady state over about 100 ms. Taking into account the transition of operating modes over time in the RDC, the last 50 ms of the full spectrum are usually used for evaluation. The combined pressure signal for each axial location is obtained by summing up the dynamic component and the time-averaged static pressure offset, which provides an estimate of the static pressure variation.

In order to find the representative features within a detonation lap, the arithmetic averaging method is then used to perform phase averaging on the pressure signal. In this study, cases of single wave modes (SW) [22] are focused on as a starting point to understand the pressure field of the RDC based on the experimental data, in which only one primary

wave can be observed near the detonation zone at 25.6 mm. First, the peak position of the primary wave in each lap is defined, and then each lap with the lap before and after it are treated as a time window, so that the 50 ms evaluation section can be cut up into multiple time windows, including three adjacent laps. Finally, the pressure traces are averaged over all time windows using arithmetic averaging by aligning the peak positions of the middle laps given in figure 2(b), which shows the average pressure curve in black and underlying data in grey. The reason for defining a window with three laps instead of one is for the visibility of the second outlet reflection propagation, which will be discussed in the following section. More detailed description of the phase-averaging procedures can be found in [12].

Fig. 2 Averaging procedures: (a) pressure traces from a PCB sensor and a CTAP probe (b) phase averaged results at each axial location based on the combined signal, $\dot{m} = 500 \text{ g/s}$ and $A_8/A_{3.2} = 0.67$.

B. Circumferential structure of the pressure field

After the above mentioned phased-average pressure extraction process, taking the case with 33% outlet restriction and 500 g/s mass flow rate as an example, a pressure field map is built in Figure 3a, in which the dark blue background between the sensors is the regions without diagnostic information, each horizontal bright band represents the phase-averaged pressure within three detonation laps at each axial location, and the color bar shows the pressure amplitude, which is scaled to a specific range in order for the circumferential structure to be clearly visible. For the same reason, only the dynamic pressure is used for this map, which can eliminate the influence of the static pressure offset from CTAP on the key features of the structure. The two red lines represent the physical locations of the combustor exit (dash line) and exit throat (solid line) respectively. The pressure at 117.6 mm, which is not shown here, is because the fifth pair of sensors is mounted outside the combustor exit and this region is not the focus in this study. It can be seen that three detonation laps propagate from right to left. The red circles represent detonation/oblique shock. The yellow circles represent an inlet reflection caused by the collision of the detonation front and the inlet boundary. When these two waves propagate downstream and encounter the outlet boundaries, their corresponding reflections (marked as green and pink circles) propagate from downstream to upstream, which are identified as first and second outlet reflection, respectively, in this study. The comparison with simulation results in the last section shows that pressure region at 25.6 mm should be located near the triple point inside the RDC connecting the upper end of the detonation front and the starting point of the oblique shock, so all red circles are grouped as detonation/oblique shock.

Determining the position of these circles based on the pressure field diagram is a challenging task but can help us better understand the underlying mechanics of wave propagation within the RDC. Figure 3b shows the relative position of the four components (detonation/oblique shock, first outlet reflection, first inlet reflection and second outlet reflection) in three detonation laps at each axial location of the combustor. The detonation/oblique shock in red always represents the highest pressure rise in one detonation lap, making it the easiest component to identify. The positions of the yellow circles correspond to a small pressure rise after the primary peak at location 25.6 mm, 48.6 mm and 71.6 mm. This secondary peak is also observed numerically [23] and experimentally [24, 25] by other researchers, which is probably

attributable to a radial shock wave generated by the collision of detonation front with the combustion chamber wall. The yellow circle was observed to propagate from upstream to downstream and reflect back to the inlet in this study, so we will follow the hypothesis and name the yellow circles as first inlet reflection in the subsequent discussion. A further validation of this feature is being investigated with higher sensor density along the combustor axial direction. The results in Figure 4(e) and Figure 5(e) found that, at 25.6 mm, the higher the amplitude of the subsequent yellow secondary peak usually corresponds to the smaller the amplitude of the red primary peak. Chacon and Gamba [26] found the parasitic combustion in front of the detonation front, which might lead to the insufficient heat flux to support the primary wave but more sufficient for the yellow secondary wave. At 94.6 mm, the position of the yellow circle switches to the third pressure rise, and the first outlet reflection, represented by green circle, takes the position of the second peak after the red primary peak. The result in Figure 5 shows that the amplitude of the second peak at 94.6 mm is significantly affected by the outlet boundaries and increases with increasing outlet restriction, so the second pressure rise at 94.6 mm is considered to correspond to the outlet reflection. More details are discussed in sections D and E. A similar tendency of the green circles to be affected by the outlet boundary can be found at 48.6 mm and 71.6 mm, which is the basis to define their positions by combining their possible propagation paths and relative amplitudes. Since the amplitude of the second outlet reflection is small compared to the other three components, it is the most difficult component to identify. The pink circle at 94.6 mm is assigned to the fourth peak after the primary wave, which is caused by the collision of the yellow inlet reflection as it propagates to the exit. Its positions at 48.6 mm and 71.6 mm belong to the minimum peak within one detonation lap. Both first and second outlet reflection in green and pink are not shown at 25.6 mm, because at this location, pressure signals are drastically influenced by the inlet boundary and show multiple tiny peaks, given in Figure 3b, it is therefore best to temporarily exclude them from the analysis before conducting investigations with higher pressure resolution by installing more sensors in this area.

C. Impact of the mass flow rate

Figure 4 illustrates the influence of the mass flow rate on the pressure field inside the RDC with outlet restriction of 33%, where Figure 4(a)-(d) show the phased-averaged pressure of 400 g/s, 450 g/s and 500 g/s at four axial locations along the combustor. Four components are shown at 48.6 mm, 71.6 mm 94.6 mm, while only two are marked at 25.6 mm due to the complex signals affected by inlet boundary. The positions of these components are defined based on the analysis in previous section.

The pressure profile at each axial position are quite similar as the mass flow rate changes. More details of the two black rectangles are shown in Figure 4(e) and Figure 4(f). It can be seen from Figure 4(e) that the primary peaks of 450 g/s and 500 g/s are very similar albeit larger than that of 400 g/s, while the secondary peak of 400 g/s shows the largest amplitude. The red primary peak at 25.6 mm is identified as the detonation/oblique shock. The dominant frequencies in the 450 g/s and 500 g/s cases are 6.4 kHz and 6.3 kHz respectively, while the 400 g/s case is 6.1 kHz, which may partly explain the difference in their red primary peak amplitudes. As shown in Figure 4(f), under the identical outlet boundary condition, the primary peaks of 450 g/s and 500 g/s at 94.6 mm are consistently larger than that of 400 g/s. The first outlet reflection in green propagates in the opposite direction of the red oblique shock wave, so the pattern of 400 g/s-450 g/s-500 g/s can be seen in Figure 4(f), indicating that the first reflection of 500 g/s reflected first, followed by 450 g/s and 400g/s, although the dominant frequency of 500 g/s is slightly lower than 450 g/s. The amplitude of the first outlet reflection is up to two factors: the outlet boundary and the intensity of the incoming oblique shock, so the amplitude of the green circles follows the same trend as observed for primary peak with varying mass flow rate. The small peaks after the pink peaks are highly repeatable for the tests in this study and show the same amplitude for different mass flow rates, which may be caused by reflections in the radial direction of the combustor, but requires further verification.

Figure 4(g) shows the propagation path of each component by connecting their peak positions. The results show that under the same outlet boundary condition, the oblique shock and the first outlet reflection propagate nearly linearly and the two paths intersect at a point near the exit plane of the combustor which is marked in black. The slope of the line connecting the red circles is used to determine the oblique shock angle. As the mass flow rate increases, the calculated oblique shock angle increase slightly, varying from 50.0 ° to 51.4 °, which shows that mass flow rate has little influence on the oblique shock angle. It is worth mentioning that the mass flow rate variation in this study is not large because we wanted to stay within the single wave mode. A greater change of oblique shock angle will be seen with the greater mass flow rate variation. The paths of the first inlet reflection and the second outlet reflection are not completely linear, which may be limited by the low resolution of current pressure measurements. Figure 8a shows a summary of how each feature at 25.6 mm and 94.6 mm changes with the increasing mass flow rate. Note that pressure rise is measured from

(a)

(b)

Fig. 3 Circumferential structure based on dynamic pressure: (a) pressure field map (b) phase averaged results along the combustor axial direction, $\dot{m} = 500$ g/s and $A_8/A_{3.2} = 0.67$.

the initial rise point of each peak to its summit.

D. Impact of the outlet restriction

Two sets of outlet restrictions were used in this study, including uniform outlet restriction (UR) and nozzle guide vanes outlet restriction (NGVR). Their influence on the pressure field will be discussed in this section and the next section, respectively. Figure 5(a)-(f) illustrates the effect of outlet restrictions on the pressure field inside the RDC when the mass flow rate is 500 g/s. It can be seen that the oblique shock amplitude deviates more under different outlet restrictions when the oblique shock propagates downstream because the effect of the exit boundary becomes stronger near the exit. Compared with the other outlet restrictions at the same axial location, the oblique shock amplitude of UR33 is the lowest at 25.6 mm, while oblique shock wave amplitude of UR00 is the lowest at 94.6 mm because there is no blockage to enhance the pressure rise.

It can be seen from the enlarged view of Figure 5(e), that the amplitude of the detonation/oblique shock peak is less affected by the outlet boundary compared with the mass flow rate. The primary peak of 0% outlet are supposed to be the highest, but maybe due to the insufficient heat flux to support primary wave, so it becomes the lowest, see Figure 8b. Figure 5(f) shows that the primary peak in red and the first outlet reflection in green increase with the increasing outlet restriction, which means the pressure field at 94.6 mm is greatly affected by the outlet boundary, while supporting the identification of these components in section C. The first inlet reflection in yellow and second outlet reflection in pink show the same trend, and the amplitudes of these features are in good agreement with the outlet boundary conditions.

Fig. 4 Pressure field based on dynamic pressure with varied mass flow rate, $\dot{m} = 400, 450$ and 500 g/s and $A_8/A_{3.2} = 0.67$.

Note that UR00 does not have any restriction, so the pressure rise of the first and the second outlet reflection is mainly contributed by the back pressure and the combustor wall reflection, and the latter factor must be greater than the first one, so the pink second outlet reflection of UR00 is not labeled in Figure 5(f).

Figure 5(g) compares the propagation paths of each component under varying outlet restrictions. The route of UR00 is significantly out of place compared with other three outlets, which illustrates the impact of the back pressure on the pressure field inside the RDC and explains why the UR00 configuration generally showed different RDC operation in previous work [6]. The intersection points of oblique shock wave and the first outlet reflection show that flow was reflected at the combustor exit for all restricted cases (UR16, UR25 and UR33), but the intersection point of unrestricted (UR00) case exits upstream of the combustor exit. The calculated oblique shock angle continues to decrease from 65.4° to 50.0° as the outlet restrictions increases, all falling within the range of Klopsch's simulation results[21].

Fig. 5 Pressure field based on dynamic pressure measurement with varied uniform outlet restrictions, $\dot{m} = 500$ g/s and $A_8/A_{3.2} = 1, 0.84, 0.75,$ and 0.67 .

E. Impact of the discrete outlet boundaries

Figure 6 compares the pressure field map with 33% uniform outlet restriction and 33% NGVs at the combustor exit respectively. The red dashed and solid lines mark the locations of the combustor exit and exit throat, corresponding

to the leading edge and maximum cross section for NGVs. The difference between uniform outlet and NGVs is very obvious downstream. It can be seen that, in Figure 6, NGVs allow the oblique shock to pass through the red lines, so there is an obvious time delay between signals at 94.6 mm and 117.6 mm, compared to the uniform outlet, which is just a plate and blocks or reflects all the oblique shocks uniformly upstream. The fifth bright band of UR33 case in Figure 6 is due only to the exhausting gas products. In addition, the pressure signal of the NGVs at 117.6 mm shows more discrete peaks due to reflection caused by the flow bouncing between adjacent NGVs. It is clear to see that in Figure 6 by switching the uniform outlet plate to NGVs, the first reflection at different axial locations (green circles) is significantly weakened due to the reflection downstream of the NGVs.

Figures 7(a)-(e) show the position of each component along the axial direction of the combustor for different outlet setups and restrictions with 500 g/s mass flow rate. Note that nine NGVs provides 17% blockage at the combustor exit and the corresponding uniform outlet plate is 16%. Figure 7(g) shows the amplitudes of oblique shock peaks at 98.6 mm grouped according to the outlet restriction, NGVR33 and UR33 show the similar peak value and the same is true for NGVR17 and UR16, which shows that the amplitude of this region are mainly controlled by the boundary conditions. The first outlet reflection in green of NGV17 and NGV33 is significantly reduced compared with the corresponding uniform outlet, indicating that discrete outlet boundary can effectively reduce fluctuations in the combustor. Figure 7(h) shows the for 33% outlet blockage, the installation of NGVs instead of uniform outlets can increase the oblique shock angle from 50.0° to 54.3° . The intersection points of oblique shock wave and the first outlet reflection in Figure 7(g) show that flow was reflected near the combustor exit.

Figure 8a and Figure 8b show that at 25.6 mm, the effect of mass flow rate on the pressure rise of the oblique shock wave is greater than the effect of the outlet restriction on the pressure rise of the oblique shock wave. However, at 94.6 mm close to the outlet boundary, the impact of the outlet restriction on the pressure rise of the oblique shock wave is greater. At 94.6 mm, the change of the first outlet reflection pressure rise is generally consistent with the change of the oblique shock wave pressure rise, which is mainly affected by the outlet boundary conditions. In addition, at 25.6 mm, the stronger pressure rise of the oblique shock wave generally corresponds to the weaker pressure rise of the first inlet reflection. Figure 8c shows the peak amplitudes summarized for the component variations influenced by NGVs previously discussed, where we can see the oblique shock pressure rise at 25.6 mm decreases with the increasing restriction from 16% to 33%, but remains constant within the same blockage of both uniform outlet and NGVs. The first inlet reflection pressure rise at the same axial position has a tendency to wax and wane with the oblique shock peak. Pressure signals at 94.6 mm are significantly influenced by the outlet boundaries so the oblique shock in red, first outlet reflection in green and second outlet reflection in pink are strongly linked to the specific outlet condition, meaning that the higher restriction, the stronger pressure rise of these three components, Note that the first outlet reflection pressure rise of NGVR33 should be similar to that of UR33, but as analysed above, the flow bounce between NGVs weakens the outlet reflection. For NGVR17, the azimuthal interval is larger than for NGV33, so the elimination of outlet reflection is less obvious.

F. Comparison with the fast reactive Euler solver-based simulation results

Figure 9 compares the experimental data in this study with simulation results based on a fast reactive Euler solver developed by [21] for the configuration mentioned in the experimental setup section. Only one detonation lap is shown in Figure 9 and the combined signal is used to build the upper experimental pressure field map to compare the complete information of the static pressure with the simulation. The color bar has been scaled to the range where the circumferential structure can be seen more clearly. As can be seen from the figure, the two components of detonation/oblique shock wave in red and first outlet reflection in green observed in the experimental data are clearly visible and align very well with the simulated pressure map. The first inlet reflection in yellow at 25.4 mm in the simulation results matches well with the pressure rise in the experimental map. However, the other positions of the first inlet reflection and the second outlet reflection in pink cannot be clearly observed in the simulation map. Considering their smaller amplitudes, they most likely overlap with the fields passed by the red oblique shock and green outlet reflection. The oblique shock angles are also comparable between the figures, 50.0° in the experiment and 52.7° in the simulation. In general, the experimental map built based on five pairs of PCBs and CTAPs in this study are in good agreement with the simulation results, however a higher resolution in the experiment would further aid in this analysis. It is worth mentioning that the pressure maps based on experimental results and simulation results are also comparable for other cases, here only taking the case with 33% outlet restriction and 500g/s mass flow rate as an example for the consistency of the whole paper.

Fig. 6 Comparison of uniform outlet restriction and NGVs: pressure field map, $\dot{m} = 500 \text{ g/s}$ and $A_8/A_{3.2} = 0.67$.

Fig. 7 Comparison of uniform outlet restriction and NGVs: phase averaged results based on dynamic pressure, $\dot{m} = 500 \text{ g/s}$ and $A_8/A_{3.2} = 0.84$ and 0.67 .

Fig. 8 Pressure rise influenced by (a) mass flow rates (b) uniform outlet restrictions and (c) discrete outlet boundaries.

Fig. 9 Pressure field map comparison based experimental data and simulation results, $\dot{m} = 500$ g/s and $A_8/A_{3.2} = 0.67$.

IV. Conclusions

This paper has tried to measure the pressure field map inside the RDC based on experimental data through a combination of dynamic and averaged-static pressure measurement matrix. In single wave (SW) operating mode test cases, four key components including detonation/oblique shock and one inlet reflection both propagating downstream, and two outlet reflections propagating upstream were observed based on the phased-averaged pressure, which provides a reference to identify each pressure rise in a detonation lap, along the axial location of the combustor and further helps the understanding of the circumferential structure of the pressure field inside the RDC. The effects of the mass flow rate and the outlet restrictions on pressure rise and oblique shock angle are investigated. In addition, a set of nozzle guide vanes are installed at the combustor exit to compare with the uniform outlet plane as an preliminary exploration of the integration possibility of the RDC on a gas turbine. In the end, a numerical pressure map simulated by a fast reactive Euler solver was compared with the experiment-based pressure map under the same configuration, and good agreement between the two plots was found.

Pressure rise due to the detonation wave propagation at four axial locations inside the RDC is identified. Based on the three neighboring detonation laps time window, detonation/oblique shock is assigned to the first primary pressure rise in one detonation lap. The ensuing secondary small pressure rise represents the shock wave generated by the detonation front hitting the combustor wall. The propagation of these two components is blocked by the outlet boundary, and then produces their corresponding reflections that propagate upstream and interact with the upstream pressure field.

In the single wave mode region investigated in this study, the mass flow rate variations have minimal influence on the pressure rise and oblique shock angle, while the outlet restrictions show a significant impact on the downstream pressure profile and oblique shock angle. The pressure rise caused by the detonation/oblique shock and the pressure rise caused by the inlet reflection have a tendency to wax and wane in the detonation region. The pressure rise of the first outlet reflection and the oblique shock angle show a strong correspondence with the outlet boundary. The more restricted the outlet is, the higher the peak pressure of the first reflection at the combustion chamber exit is and the smaller the oblique shock wave angle is.

Installing NGVs can effectively reduced downstream reflections that can interact with the upstream pressure field, indicating that NGVs are promising in reducing fluctuations inside the RDC. For a 33% blockage at the combustor exit, the oblique shock angle increases 4° after installing the NGVs compared to the corresponding uniform outlet. Reflections between NGVs complicate the pressure field and are not the focus of this study, but it will be interesting to investigate the pressure elimination and enhancement phenomenon in the NGVs section in the following research with higher sensor density.

One specific configuration of 33% outlet restriction and 500 g/s mass flow rate is compared between the pressure from experimental results and the simulation. The results show that the key components of detonation/oblique shock and first outlet reflection identified in experiments are well observed in the simulation map. The inlet reflection can be partially observed due to its smaller intensity compared to the the other two components. The oblique shock angle variation is less than 3° .

In general, this work illustrates the process of obtaining the phase-average pressure and establishing the pressure map inside the RDC, provides a reference for identifying the pressure rise throughout the combustor and investigating the possibility of turbine integration with a set of nozzle guide vanes. Although higher-resolution pressure maps need to be established to further validate the findings, the current work still shows the great potential to experimentally reveal the true static pressure field inside the RDC with varying outlet boundaries.

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